

DEVELOPMENT OF A 2-BIT CMOS DECODER

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Abstract – This work presents, in a summarized manner, the development and simulation of a 2-bit CMOS decoder, using the LTSpice XVII software as an aid. The present circuit operates with 2 inputs, one of which is responsible for the cooling system and the other being the signal from a temperature sensor.

Keywords: decoder; CMOS; LTSpice; cooling system; temperature sensor.

INTRODUCTION

A CMOS decoder is an electronic circuit used to decode digital signals and convert these signals into a set of logical outputs [1], which are used to control other digital devices such as integrated circuits, microcontrollers, among others.

The CMOS (Complementary Metal-Oxide-Semiconductor) circuit is composed of complementary transistors, a PMOS and an NMOS, which work together to produce a logical output. The CMOS decoder is a logic circuit that detects a set of binary inputs and produces a corresponding logical output [2]. The logical output is determined by the detected binary input pattern. CMOS decoders are commonly used in digital applications, such as, using the developed circuit as an example, a temperature control system. The circuit can be designed to detect various binary input patterns, ranging from 2 to 8 inputs, and this factor varies depending on the application.

CMOS decoders can also be designed to work in conjunction with other logic circuits [3], such as AND, OR, XOR, and NAND circuits, to create more complex and sophisticated circuits. Additionally, they can be used in conjunction with other types of circuits, such as multiplexers and demultiplexers, to create more complete and efficient digital systems.

DEVELOPMENT

Truth tables were constructed to identify the circuit's operation and logic. For the construction of the truth table, some parameters were defined: T1 is the signal that indicates when the process reaches the set point, activating the cooling system; T2 is the temperature sensor responsible for indicating whether the temperature is above 25% of the set point value. If T2 is activated but T1 is not, it means that T1 has a problem, thus activating the safety system and triggering the alarm.

TABLE 1 - Truth table of the circuit

T1	T2	SR	AL	DLA
0	0	0	0	0
0	1	1	1	1
1	0	1	0	0
1	1	1	1	0

Given the truth table, it was identified that the circuit has two inputs (T1 and T2) and three outputs: SR (Cooling sensor); AL (alarm); DLA (Heating system off). Thus, obtaining the following model:

Figure 1 – Circuit diagram from the truth table.

Based on the above diagram, the circuit was developed in the LTSpice XVII software, where the circuit's behavior was analyzed to validate it according to the established parameters for the circuit's construction.

Figure 2 – 2-bit CMOS decoder circuit.

It should be noted that each logic gate is made up of an internal CMOS circuit, as shown in the following images:

Figure 3 – AND gate circuit.

